

Volumetric and viscometric studies on 1,4-dioxane and methanol binary mixtures at different temperatures

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Abstract : Densities and viscosities of binary liquid mixtures of 1,4-dioxane with polar solvent viz. methanol have been measured at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K. From the density and viscosity data, the values of various properties viz. excess molar volume (V^E), excess viscosity (η^E) and excess Gibb's free energy of activation of flow (ΔG^E) have been determined. Further the viscosities of binary mixtures have been correlated to various viscosity models.

On the basis of the values of interaction parameters of these viscosity models and also on the basis of the values of various excess properties, the nature of molecular interactions between the components of mixtures have been explained.

Keywords : Viscometric studies, mixed solvent, binary mixture (1,4-dioxane and methanol), viscosity models (equations).

Introduction

The thermodynamic and transport properties of 1,4-dioxane with methanol have been studied over the entire composition range, at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K. The present study reveals the nature and extent of interactions between the component molecules in their binary mixtures.

In the present paper densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of binary mixtures of 1,4-dioxane with methanol covering the entire composition range (expressed by mole fraction x of 1,4-dioxane) at 305.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K are reported. From experimental values of densities and viscosities excess molar volume (V^E), excess viscosity (η^E), excess free energy of activation of viscous flow (ΔG^E) of methanol in 1,4-dioxane have been calculated. These functions offer a convenient approach for the study of thermodynamic properties of liquid mixtures. The extreme sensitivity of excess functions is due to the size, shape of the molecule and interaction among themselves and gives important information about inter molecular forces which are responsible for these interactions.

The several models (equations) have been used from time to time for correlating the viscosity of binary mixtures with those of component liquid systems, and have been used to test the reliability of the results.

Results and discussion

The excess function is a measure of deviation from the ideal behavior of the mixture, and found to be highly sensitive towards molecular interactions between the component molecules of liquid mixtures. The sign and magnitude of these excess functions from ideality depends on the strength of interaction between unlike molecules.

Excess molar volume (V^E) : The excess molar volume (V^E) of binary mixture was evaluated from the molar volume of mixture (V) and that of pure components (V_1 and V_2).

Using the following equation¹,

$$V^E = V - (x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2) \quad (1)$$

Note

Table 1. Densities, viscosities, excess properties and interaction parameters (d_{12} , T_{12} , H_{12}) of binary liquid mixtures of methanol and 1,4-dioxane at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K

Sr. no.	x_1	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	τ^E (mPa.s)	v^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^E (J mol ⁻¹)	d_{12}	T_{12}	H_{12}
303.15 K									
1.	0.0000	1.0204	1.0661	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2.	0.2341	1.0019	1.0407	0.1049	-0.8800	454.77	0.8300	0.0725	1.0803
3.	0.4074	0.9777	1.0026	0.1633	-1.1000	721.07	0.9922	0.1035	1.1259
4.	0.6470	0.9241	0.8778	0.1719	-0.8920	843.81	1.2418	0.1009	1.1641
5.	0.8048	0.8723	0.7408	0.1228	-0.5410	680.22	1.4672	0.0677	1.1785
6.	0.9166	0.8249	0.6242	0.0685	-0.2350	410.42	1.8553	0.0314	1.2354
7.	0.9397	0.8139	0.5943	0.0514	-0.1760	316.45	1.9378	0.0228	1.2414
8.	0.9611	0.8031	0.5637	0.0327	-0.1130	210.09	1.9458	0.0146	1.2255
9.	1.0000	0.7823	0.5093	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
308.15 K									
1.	0.0000	1.0160	0.9621	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2.	0.2341	0.9966	0.9393	0.0969	-0.8290	475.14	0.8555	0.0656	0.9766
3.	0.4074	0.9725	0.9035	0.1497	-1.0710	749.32	1.0182	0.0936	1.0164
4.	0.6470	0.9184	0.7926	0.1612	-0.8490	891.60	1.2978	0.0915	1.0594
5.	0.8048	0.8669	0.9976	0.1169	-0.5200	727.15	1.5121	0.0611	1.1287
6.	0.9166	0.8196	0.5555	0.0619	-0.2240	426.10	1.8996	0.0280	1.1112
7.	0.9397	0.8085	0.5259	0.0441	-0.1560	317.58	1.9052	0.0202	1.0955
8.	0.9611	0.7980	0.4978	0.0269	-0.1090	204.40	1.8525	0.0129	1.0665
9.	1.0000	0.7772	0.4510	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
313.15 K									
1.	0.0000	1.0156	0.8783	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2.	0.2341	0.9951	0.8535	0.0849	-0.8000	472.84	0.8359	0.0598	0.8807
3.	0.4074	0.9699	0.8201	0.1327	-1.0170	751.18	1.0028	0.0852	0.9188
4.	0.6470	0.9150	0.7198	0.1447	-0.8220	898.97	1.2889	0.0834	0.9607
5.	0.8048	0.8624	0.6047	0.1035	-0.4860	728.42	1.5306	0.0554	0.9735
6.	0.9166	0.8148	0.5013	0.0526	-0.2060	414.21	1.8076	0.0252	0.9875
7.	0.9397	0.8034	0.4731	0.0352	-0.1360	296.86	1.7277	0.0181	0.9541
8.	0.9611	0.7926	0.4518	0.0239	-0.0800	206.00	1.8229	0.0117	0.9632
9.	1.0000	0.7721	0.4097	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
318.15 K									
1.	0.0000	1.0112	0.8179	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2.	0.2341	0.9907	0.7961	0.0810	-0.7950	489.72	0.8543	0.0558	0.8242
3.	0.4074	0.9650	0.7683	0.1292	-0.9700	789.31	1.0398	0.0800	0.8661
4.	0.6470	0.9110	0.6709	0.1371	-0.8060	929.05	1.3131	0.0779	0.8984
5.	0.8048	0.8586	0.5637	0.0992	-0.4650	759.48	1.5739	0.0518	0.9140
6.	0.9166	0.8112	0.4646	0.0492	-0.1820	427.19	1.8310	0.0234	0.9200
7.	0.9397	0.8002	0.4381	0.0328	-0.1290	305.08	1.7476	0.0168	0.8879
8.	0.9611	0.7893	0.4168	0.0209	-0.0650	203.71	1.7561	0.0108	0.8781
9.	1.0000	0.7692	0.3788	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

The molar volumes V of the binary liquid mixture were calculated from the measured density (ρ) of the mixture using following equation²,

$$V = (x_1 M_1) + (x_2 M_2)/\rho \quad (2)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the mole fractions of component 1 and 2 of binary liquid mixtures respectively, V_1 is M_1/ρ_1 and V_2 is M_2/ρ_2 . ρ_1 and ρ_2 are densities of components 1 and 2 respectively.

The excess viscosity (η^E) of the given binary liquid mixture was calculated from the observed viscosity of mixture and that of its pure components using following equation³,

$$\eta^E = \eta - (x_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \eta_2) \quad (3)$$

where η is viscosity of binary mixture, η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of pure component 1 and 2 respectively and x_1 and x_2 are the mole fractions of the components 1 and 2 respectively.

The excess Gibb's free energy of flow (ΔG^E) for the binary liquid mixture was computed from the Eyring equation⁶,

$$\Delta G^E = RT (\ln \eta V - x_1 \ln \eta_1 V_1 - x_2 \ln \eta_2 V_2) \quad (4)$$

where the symbols have their usual significance.

The values of density (ρ), viscosity (η), molar volume (V) and excess thermodynamic properties viz. excess molar volume (V^E), excess viscosity (η^E), excess Gibb's free energy of activation of flow (ΔG^E) at various temperatures 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K as a function of composition of binary mixtures have been presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Variation of excess molar volumes (V^E) with mole fraction (x_1) for methanol (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K.

A perusal of Table 1 shows the values of V^E of binary mixture of 1,4-dioxane + methanol are negative over entire range of composition and for all experimental temperatures. The Fig. 1 exhibits the variation of V^E with mole fraction x_1 of methanol at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K. Increase in temperature from 303.15 to 318.15 K results in decrease in the V^E for 1,4-dioxane + methanol.

The negative values of V^E are due to the chemical or specific interactions which can result in decrease in volume and these include possible depolymerisation of self associated alcohol by the addition of 1,4-dioxane or formation of new bonds (hydrogen bond) between 1,4-dioxane and alcohol and other complex forming interactions.

All the values V^E are fitted to Redlich-Kister type polynomial⁵,

$$V^E = x_1 x_2 \sum a_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (5)$$

The values of parameters obtained by least square method are included in Table 2.

The standard deviation (σ) calculated as

$$\sigma(V^E) = [(\sum V^E_{\text{experimental}} - V^E_{\text{calculated}})^2 / (D - N)]^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where D is number of experimental data points and N is number of parameters.

The values of standard deviation at different temperatures for methyl alcohol are of the order 10^{-3} .

A perusal of Table 1 shows that the values of η^E are positive over entire range of composition and at all experimental temperatures. The negative of η^E suggest

Fig. 2. Variation of excess viscosity (η^E) with mole fraction (x_1) for methanol (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K.

Table 2. Redlich-Kister co-efficient of excess molar volume and standard deviation for methanol (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K

Temp. (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	σ
303.15	-4.3109	1.2709	0.2267	3.1×10^{-3}
308.15	-4.1667	1.1843	0.4350	1.02×10^{-3}
313.15	-4.0120	1.1758	0.6174	5.8×10^{-3}
318.15	-3.8889	1.2253	0.6030	1.33×10^{-3}

Table 3. Redlich-Kister co-efficient of excess molar viscosity and standard deviation for methanol (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K

Temp. (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	σ
303.15	0.70036	0.18895	-0.01497	2.8×10^{-3}
308.15	0.65527	0.18868	-0.05138	1.6×10^{-3}
313.15	0.58878	0.17174	-0.09652	1.5×10^{-3}
318.15	0.65527	0.18668	-0.05138	1.6×10^{-3}

Fig. 3. Variation of excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow (ΔG^E) with mole fraction (x_1) for methanol (1) + 1,4-dioxane (2) at 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K.

that dispersion types⁶ of forces are predominant in these mixtures while positive values may be attributed to the presence of strong interactions⁷. The plot of η^E against x_1 (mole fraction of alcohol) for the binary mixtures have been presented in the Fig. 2.

The values of ΔG^E for binary mixtures 1,4-dioxane and alcohol have been presented in Table 1. It is seen that the values of ΔG^E are positive over entire range of composition for methanol. The values of ΔG^E for above binary mixtures have been plotted against x_1 , the plots have been represented in Fig. 3. The plots are parabolic in shape. The negative values of ΔG^E may be attributed to the dominance of dispersion forces while positive one to the size effect of the mixing components⁸. According to Mayer⁹, ΔG^E may be considered as a reliable measure to detect the presence of interaction between the molecule, positive values of ΔG^E can be seen in binary mixture where specific interactions

(hydrogen bonding) between the molecules are dominant where as negative ΔG^E indicates characteristic behavior of mixture in which dispersion forces are dominant¹⁰.

Viscosity models and interaction parameters : The several models (equation have been put forward for correlating the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures with those of component liquid with a view to interpret the molecular interaction in the liquid mixture in terms of interaction parameter of the viscosity model.

Grunberg and Nissan¹¹ have suggested the following logarithmic relation between viscosity of the binary liquid mixture and pure components.

$$\ln \eta = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 d_{12} \quad (7)$$

where d_{12} is constant proportional to interaction energy it is approximate measure of strength of the molecular interaction between the mixing components.

Tumara and Kurata developed the following equation for the viscosity of binary mixture¹²,

$$\eta = x_1 \Phi_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \Phi_2 \eta_2 + 2(x_1 x_2 \Phi_1 \Phi_2)^{0.5} T_{12} \quad (8)$$

where T_{12} is interaction parameter and depends on temperature and composition of mixture. Φ_1, Φ_2 are the volume fractions and x_1, x_2 are mole fractions, η_1 and η_2 are viscosities of pure components 1 and 2 respectively.

Hind *et al.* suggests the following equation for the viscosity of binary mixtures,

$$\eta = x_1^2 \eta_1 + x_2^2 \eta_2 + 2x_1x_2 H_{12} \quad (9)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the mole fraction, η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of liquid components 1 and 2 respectively. η is viscosity of binary mixture and H_{12} is Hind interaction parameter.

The value of d_{12} (vide eq. (7)) provide better measure of strength of interaction³. The variation with composition is large where strong specific interaction might be expected which vary with composition.

The values of T_{12} and H_{12} (vide eqs. (8) and (9)) for given mixture T_{12} and H_{12} do not show very different variation except where there is a strong interaction between the components¹⁴.

A perusal of values of T_{12} and H_{12} shows that they are positive for all the binary mixtures, showing strong specific interactions.

Experimental

1,4-Dioxane and methanol were from S.D. fine chemicals (spectroscopic HPLC, A.R. grade) and were further purified according to standard procedures¹⁵. The purities were checked by comparing their densities and viscosities with literature values (in the accuracy $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g cm³ and $\pm 3 \times 10^{-3}$ mPa.s respectively).

The densities of pure liquids and their binary mixtures were measured using a single capillary pycnometer (made up of Borosil glass) having bulb capacity of 8×10^{-3} m³. Viscosities of pure liquid and their binary mixture were measured using Ubbelohde type suspended level viscometer calibrated with triple distilled water. The viscometers containing the test liquid were allowed to stand for about 30 min in

thermostatic bath. The thermostatically controlled water bath whose temperature was maintained constant by circulating water through Julabo F 25 MP thermostat (made in Germany) thermostatically controlled water bath, capable of maintaining constant temperature (± 0.02 °C).

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